

ПОМИДОР МЕВАЛАРИНИ САҚЛАШ

ЖУРАБОВА ШОХСАНАМ МАМАШОКИР ҚИЗИ

*Андижон қишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти
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АХМЕДОВА ДИЛНОЗА АБДУВАХОБ ҚИЗИ

Андижон қишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти талабалари

Аннотация. Ушбу тезисда сабзаёт экинларидан бири бўлган помидор ўсимлигининг хусусиятлари, ахамияти, пишган помидор қизил мевасининг биокимёвий таркиби, помидор ҳосилини сақлаш шароити ва яшиқларга жойланган помидорларни омборларга жойлаштириш тартиби ҳақида ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: помидор (пушти, оч кўк ва кўк ранг) ахамияти, таркиби, яшиқ, омбор, сақлаш, ҳарорат, намлик.

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Аннотация. В данной дипломной работе описаны характеристика и значение растения томата, являющегося одной из овощных культур, биохимический состав спелых красных плодов томата, условия хранения урожая томатов и порядок хранения томатов в ящиках.

Ключевые слова: Значение помидоров (розовые, голубые и голубые), состав, ящик, склад, хранение, температура, влажность.

STORAGE OF TOMATOES

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Annotation. This thesis describes the characteristics and importance of the tomato plant, which is one of the vegetable crops, the biochemical composition of ripe tomato red fruit, storage conditions of tomato crop and the order of storage of tomatoes in boxes.

Keywords: The importance of tomatoes (pink, light blue and blue), composition, box, warehouse, storage, temperature, humidity.

Tomato is a plant belonging to the family *Solanum lycopersicum* and is one of the most loved vegetables in the world. The plant is native to Peru and Ecuador, South America. To this day, wild species can be found in Mexico. This plant was first cultivated in Mexico. The Aztecs called this plant "tumantla". After the Spanish conquest of Mexico in 1523, its wild seeds were added to other plants and came to Europe. In 1554, the Spanish botanist Pero Andrea Mattioli and others wrote that this plant was called poisonous, unfit for consumption. Indeed, this vegetable, which belongs to the family of alfalfa, contains alkaloid toxins, which are in small amounts and are considered safe for human life. Tomatoes are also grown in botanical fields in Europe and the Netherlands, where medicinal plants are grown. The most popular and widespread vegetable crop in Uzbekistan is tomato, which ranks first in terms of area and gross yield. Tomatoes make up 35-38% of the total area under vegetable crops. Tomato is one of the vegetable crops with high nutritional value. Its ripe fruit is extremely tasty, dietary and contains various vitamins, mineral salts, organic acids and carbohydrates. The biochemical composition of tomato red fruit is as follows:

dry matter 0.6-6.6%, protein 0.95-1.0%, sugar 4.0-5.0%, oils 0.2-0.3%, cellulose 0.8-0.9%, ash 0.6%, organic (malic, citric) acids 0.5%, vitamin C (ascorbic acid) 19-35 mg / kg, carotene (provitamin A) 0.2-2 mg / kg, thiamine (V1) 0.3-1.6 mg / kg, riboflavin (V2) 1.5-6 mg / kg. But the composition of tomato fruit is variable, it depends on factors such as crop navigation, the degree of ripening of the fruit, the time of harvest, growing conditions and technology. Tomatoes are eaten fresh, pickled and marinated. It is an important raw material for the canning (processing) industry. Tomatoes are ripe when harvested and resistant to long storage. Therefore, after harvest, the period of its consumption can be extended for another 1.0-1.5 months.

Tomatoes are more difficult to store than other vegetables. However, it can be stored for 2–3 months. Yields of 60-70 g of tomatoes, 35-50 g of small varieties are well preserved. The fruits of varieties with a high content of water are long will not be saved. The thickness of the tomato skin, the hardness of the core and the resistance to cracking determine its preservation. For storage, fully formed light blue tomatoes are picked with a bunch of fruit. They should be undamaged, free from disease and pests, and not too small.

Tomatoes are harvested when they are fully browned at different ripening levels, half-ripe (the period when they start to turn pink and brown) and turn light blue and blue. Tomatoes are stored in boxes in warehouses. In this case, the boxes are placed in two rows in width, eight to ten at the top, and as long as desired. It is recommended to leave a corridor of 0.6-1.5 m between the boxes, and 5-10 cm between the boxes. Red tomatoes can be stored for up to 30 days, tubers for 40-50 days, and blueberries for up to 80 days. It is desirable that the temperature for ripening light blue tomatoes was +10 +12 0S. At higher temperatures the ripening of tomatoes is accelerated, and at lower temperatures it quickly becomes ill. Baked tomatoes can be stored in the refrigerator at -1 0C. In this case, the relative humidity should be around 90-95%. Working tomatoes with ethylene gas for 8-10 hours a day

accelerates its ripening 3-4 times. Tomatoes should be monitored regularly during storage.

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